

INFLUENCE OF CITRIC ACID CONTENT ON THE PROPERTIES OF GYPSUM REINFORCED WITH BAMBOO PARTICLES

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ABSTRACT

Construction is among the most energy-consuming human activities, and energy is a problem on a finite planet. There is a search for new technologies that bring improvements and solutions in the optimization of low energy incorporated materials and can minimize environmental impacts. Samples were made with water/gypsum ratio of 0.5 and 0.7, and citric acid contents of 0.0%, 0.010%, 0.020% and 0.030%. Therefore, it was possible to verify the influence of citric acid contents on gypsum paste and gypsum bamboo composites. The use of citric acid and trituated bamboo in gypsum matrix proved to be effective in this research.

KEYWORDS

Gypsum; Bamboo; Citric Acid; Composites.

INTRODUCTION

According to Nguyen et al (2017), one third of the total energy produced in the Earth is consumed for heating and cooling buildings around the world and the forecast demand is only going to increase. The use of materials with low thermal conductivity can help to reduce energy consumption in this field. The use of low environmental impact materials emerges as an alternative to improve the environmental quality of buildings, so the use of biomaterials based on natural fibers have been considered relevant, as they are low carbon issuer and renewable materials (Gupta, Maji, 2019).

Therefore, bamboo has been most noticed in recent years and can be incorporated into composites, reducing environmental impacts and contributing to the development of sustainable materials. Addition of natural fibers in fragile matrices, such as gypsum pastes, is better for its mechanical, thermal and acoustic properties (Agopyan, 1998).

Gypsum is a cementitious material widely used in civil construction and can be considered a material with better performance from an environmental point of view. While Portland cement requires temperatures of around 1450 °C and emits a lot of CO₂ in the limestone decarbonisation process, gypsum can be produced at temperatures of 140 °C - 150 °C and emits water vapor (Melo, 2012).

Through a chemical reaction, the mixture between gypsum and water is converted into a powdered hemi hydrated into dihydrate (Gomes, 2012). The hydration mechanism is a chemical phenomenon responsible for viscosity gain, initial setting time, hardening, increasing paste strength and final setting time (Monteiro, 2015). Hardening and crystallization takes place through the expansion of the nuclei. If the process occurs quickly, it can generate malformed crystals, while slowly, less imperfection appeared (Agopyan, 1998).

Gypsum/water ratio (w/g) has a greater influence on the reaction kinetics and, consequently, on gypsum hardening (Silva, 2010). A lower w/g ratio leads to a faster setting due to the agility with which the hydration products are close to each other and produces the three-dimensional structure. However, an excess of water can prevent the agglomeration of the crystals but produces greater porosity (Gomes, 2012).

Gomes (2012) considers the initial and final setting times to be a limiting factor in the use of the gypsum paste. The setting time can be adequate for the purpose of use, allowing the handling of the material before the initial setting. The water needed depends on a distribution and particle size (John, Cincotto, 2007), however it can be changed with the presence of additives (Nogueira, 2012).

Accelerator additives increase the solubility of the hemihydrate, while retarders can extend the induction period, causing displacement of the hydration curve heat, or interfering with the kinetics of the dihydrate microstructural formation (Bardella, 2011). In addition, Abreu (2005) states that the retarders, used with the target of controlling the initial plaster setting time, should be dosed in the minimum amount, as all retarders reduce plaster strength.

Hincapie and Cincotto (1997) says that the effect of retarders in the hydration reaction can be divided into compounds that affect the induction period without affecting the reaction rate, such as citric acid and borax, and another group, consisting of casein and gelatin, which affect the induction period and decrease the rate of hydration reaction. Several retarders for plaster have already been studied, but according to Camarini et al (2016), in about 67% of the researches the citric acid prevails.

Although great achievement has already been obtained in using retarders with gypsum plasters, topics about energy efficiency of buildings are still being developed. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate the properties of fresh and hardened gypsum paste reinforced with bamboo particles and with the use of citric acid in order to be applied in divider panels and thermal protection.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

In this experimental program, hemi hydrated gypsum available on the local market, anhydrous citric acid and bamboo particles of the species *Bambusa vulgaris* were used, since it is the most abundant species in the region. Citric acid was used as a retarder in the gypsum mixture at concentrations 0%, 0.010%, 0.020%, and 0.030%. Bamboo was previously treated by immersion in a solution of boric acid and borax to prevent insects attack (Gomes Neto, 2017). Then, pieces of bamboo were crushed to attain the size shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Appearance of material after processing

An experimental planning was carried out in order to define the optimal composition for a balance between the amounts of citric acid added to the composite and its physical and mechanical properties.

Initially, gypsum pastes were prepared with a w/g ratio of 0.5 and 0.7 without additions, called references. The criteria for choosing the limit addition levels and w/g were in agreement with Machado (2011). After this step, the planning includes the incorporation of citric acid in the gypsum matrix. The amount of bamboo particles was 15% by mass of gypsum. In Table 1, the mixes utilized are indicated.

Table 1: Composition of the mixes

Sample	Title	W/G	Acid Citric	Bamboo
Citric Acid	RAC5-0	0.5	0.00%	0%
	RAC5-1	0.5	0.01%	0%
	RAC5-2	0.5	0.02%	0%
	RAC5-3	0.5	0.03%	0%
Citric Acid + 15% Bamboo	RB5-0	0.5	0.00%	15%
	RB5-1	0.5	0.01%	15%
	RB5-2	0.5	0.02%	15%
	RB5-3	0.5	0.03%	15%
Citric Acid	RAC7-0	0.7	0.00%	0%
	RAC7-1	0.7	0.01%	0%
	RAC7-2	0.7	0.02%	0%
	RAC7-3	0.7	0.03%	0%
Citric Acid + 15% Bamboo	RB7-0	0.7	0.00%	15%
	RB7-1	0.7	0.01%	15%
	RB7-2	0.7	0.02%	15%
	RB7-3	0.7	0.03%	15%

The samples were casted at an ambient temperature of approximately 30°C. The water was placed in a ceramic container and the plaster sprayed in water for a period of 1 minute. The paste was allowed to rest for 2 minutes and then mixed for 1 minute. After mixing, the paste was placed in the cone to perform the Vicat’s test. Cubic samples of 50 mm edge were casted for compression test and prismatic samples 40 mm x 40 mm x 160 mm were prepared for bending test. The specimens (Figure 2) for mechanical testing were dried in a ventilated environment for about 7 days until weight stability. The density was then obtained (Table 2).

Table 2: Density of samples

Title	RAC5-0	RAC5-1	RAC5-2	RAC5-3	RB5-0	RB5-1	RB5-2	RB5-3
g/cm ³	1.42	1.4	1.42	1.45	1.34	1.32	1.23	1.35
Title	RAC7-0	RAC7-1	RAC7-2	RAC7-3	RB7-0	RB7-1	RB7-2	RB7-3
g/cm ³	1.17	1.16	1.19	1.21	1.34	1.11	1.13	1.10

Figure 2: Samples for flexural tests

The paste physical properties were tested through the consistency test, initial and final setting time. The consistency tests were performed with the aid of a modified Vicat’s apparatus and guided by NBR 12128 (ABNT, 2019). Here, greater consistency means less cone penetration.

The modified Vicat’s apparatus (Figure 3a) was used to determine the paste consistency. The consistency measures the fluidity of the gypsum paste and is given by the penetration of the probe into

the modified Vicat's apparatus. In this case, the cone-shaped probe replaces the Vicat's needle. Greater probe penetration indicates a more fluid and less consistent sample. According to NBR12128 (ABNT, 2019), the consistency is considered normal when a penetration of (30+/-2) mm is obtained.

The Vicat's device determine the initial setting time (Figure 3b), that means the time gap from the moment the plaster comes into contact with the water, until the moment when the needle no longer fully penetrates into the paste and reaches approximately 1mm above the base surface. The final setting time corresponds to the time elapsed from the moment of mixing until the moment when the device needle leaves a slight impression on the paste surface.

Figure 3: Consistence (a) setting time (b) and strength (c)

Mechanical properties measured were compression strength and flexural strength NBR 12129 (ABNT, 2019) and NBR 13279 (ABNT, 2005).

To carry out the mechanical tests, a manual testing machine (Figure 3c) was used, trying to maintain a constant load speed until failure. The mechanical strength was obtained by the average strength of the 3 samples. Equation 1 gives the compressive strength (f_c) value:

$$f_c = \frac{P}{A} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Where, f_c is the compression strength; P is the rupture load and A is the cross-sectional area of the sample.

To obtain flexural strength a three point bending test was used. The distance between supports is L =100 mm.

The tensile strength in bending is given by the following equation 2:

$$f_M = \frac{3*P*L}{2*b*h^2} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where f_M is the flexural tensile strength; P is the maximum applied load; L is the distance between supports; b is the average width and h is the average height of the sample, both in the rupture section.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The consistency of the samples is shown in Figure 4. It is possible to observe all samples with a water/plaster ratio of 0.5 (Figure.4a) have lower penetration than samples with a ratio of 0.7 (Figure.4b),

indicating that samples with $w/g = 0.7$ have better fluidity and workability. This fact could be noticed during the sample molding process, as it was felt more difficult to mix samples with w/g of 0.5.

The addition of citric acid increases probe penetration indicating a lower consistency for pastes with a w/g ratio of 0.5, which was expected according to Lanzón and García-Ruiz (2012). However, the effect of citric acid in increasing the penetration of samples with w/g 0.7 has little influence, suggesting that the consistency of the paste has little influence with the addition of citric acid.

The addition of bamboo decreases probe penetration, showing that fluidity is lower and paste consistency is increased for all mixes, which was to be expected due to the entanglement of bamboo particles. However, samples with a w/g ratio of 0.5 show greater interference in consistency from the addition of bamboo than samples with a ratio of 0.7. Samples w/g of 0.5 show penetration reduction of 94%, 65%, 87% and 51%, while w/g of 0.7 presents a decrease of 9%, 20%, 28% and 28% for the percentages of 0%, 0.01%, 0.02% and 0.03% of acid citric. No influence on the consistency of interaction of mixes with citric acid and bamboo can be observed.

Mixes with a w/g ratio of 0.5 only reach the normal consistency indicated by NBR 12128 (ABNT, 2019) with the addition of citric acid, but when incrementing bamboo particles, the consistency decreases and moves away from the indicated value, while mixes with a ratio w/g of 0.7 exceed, and only reach it when bamboo particles are added.

a) Cone penetration $w/g = 0.5$

b) Cone penetration $w/g = 0.7$

Figure 4: Consistency samples $a/g = 0.5$ (a) and $a/g = 0.7$ (b)

Figures 5 present setting times results. It is possible to observe that the water/plaster ratio, addition of citric acid and presence of bamboo affect the results.

a) Setting times w/g = 0.5

b) Setting times w/g = 0,7

Figure 5: Setting times results samples with the respective additions

The increase in setting time by the addition of citric acid was already expected, according to Hincapie and Cincotto (1997). In addition, the results show that 15% addition of bamboo in the mixtures had an accelerating effect on the initial setting time, since all samples had their set start reduced, which may be due to the separation of cores and crystallization. However, it is observed that bamboo influences considerably as a delay in the final setting time for samples with the addition of 0.02% and 0.03% citric acid. In these mixtures, this occurs due to citric acid affecting the induction period, in which there is crystal growth, without affecting the reaction speed, as explained in Hincapie and Cincotto (1997). It was also observed that for all the mixtures, the increase in the increment of the addition of citric acid produces a gradual lengthening of the initial setting curve.

Workability was maintained for longer setting times. This result was obtained in commercial plaster (Lanzón, García-Ruiz, 2012). This could be seen with more evidence in the molding of the RB5-0 and

RB5-1 samples, since only a small addition of citric acid allowed enough time to cast the RB5-1 sample, while the RB5-0 sample was done with difficulty.

The compressive strength results (Figure 6) show that the material achieves better results without the addition of citric acid. This result was higher than expected by Henao and Cincotto (1997) who observed a 15% drop in mechanical properties with the addition of citrates. The addition of citric acid gradually decreases the compressive strength as the percentage of addition increases. This fact is explained by Hincapie and Cincotto (1997). They claim that the mechanical properties can be altered by modifying the crystals in the induction period. The resistance losses are 23%, 40% and 55% for samples with w/g of 0.5 and 22%, 50% and 40% for samples with w/g of 0.7. However, for samples with bamboo addition, the strength reduction due to the action of citric acid is 7%, 20% and 25% for the w/g ratio of 0.5 and 10%, 15% and 35% for the w/g ratio g of 0.7, indicating that the 15% of bamboo particles reduce the adverse effect of citric acid on compressive strength. The results also showed that the increase in the water-gypsum ratio is detrimental to the compressive strength, as stated by Antunes (1999), due to an increase in the porosity of the final product. The addition of bamboo had little influence on the compressive strength of samples with a ratio of 0.7, but showed a considerable drop to a ratio of 0.5, especially for higher citric acid contents. As the addition of citric acid increased, the drop in resistance increased proportionally for samples containing bamboo.

Figure 6: Compressive Strength

Flexural strength results (Figure 7) indicate that the material achieves better results without the addition of citric acid. The flexural strength gradually decreases as the percentage of citric acid is increased and the strength losses are 30%, 35% and 42% for samples with w/g of 0.5 and 19%, 28 % and 32% for samples with w/g of 0.7. Samples with the addition of bamboo show a reduction in strength due to the action of citric acid in the order of 10% for the w/g ratio of 0.5 and 0.7, indicating that the 15% increase in bamboo also reduces the adverse effect of the acid citrus in flexural strength. Increasing the water-gypsum ratio is detrimental to bending strength. But the addition of bamboo generated an increase in the flexural strength of samples w/g 0.5 and 0.7 containing the percentages of citric acid, however it showed a decrease in the values of sample RB5-0 when compared to RAC5-0, while the RB7-0 was superior to RAC7-0.

Figure 7: Flexural Strength

CONCLUSIONS

This early work on bamboo particles incorporation into gypsum matrices allow already draw the following conclusions:

The consistency of the gypsum pastes decreases with the increase in the water/gypsum ratio and increase with the addition of 15% bamboo particles for all the samples;

The addition of 0.01%, 0.02% and 0.03% citric acid in pastes with a water/gypsum ratio 0.5 decreases the consistency but this do not occur with the w/g =0,7;

The w/g ration influences setting time: the higher the water/plaster ratio, the longer the setting time;

The addition of citric acid proved to be efficient in increasing the gypsum setting times for any w/g ratio and the bamboo increment decreased the initial and final setting times, with the exception of mixes with citric acid at levels of 0.02% and 0.03%, which showed delayed end of setting time;

The addition of citric acid facilitates the molding of samples with a water-gypsum ratio of 0.5 and 15% of bamboo particles;

Compressive strength decreases with the addition of citric acid and incorporation of bamboo particles. But the values obtained are adequate to make plates for thermal protection and partition walls;

Flexural strength is also sufficient for the desired purposes;

Evidently from these initials results an optimization can be made to obtain the most efficient composite. Then the thermal properties of the composite will be measured and compared with other commercially available materials.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.